

Influence of Breakages of Reinforcing Elements of a Composite Orthotropic Stay Rope on Its Stress-Strain State

Ivan Belmas^{1,a}, Dmytro Kolosov^{2,b*}, Serhii Onyshchenko^{2,c}
Olena Bilous^{3,d}, Hanna Tantsura^{3,e} and Kateryna Antonova^{2,f}

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering Technology, Dniprovsk State Technical University,
2 Dniprobudivska Ave., Kamianske, 51918, Ukraine

²Department of Mechanical and Biomedical Engineering, Dnipro University of Technology,
19 Yavornytskoho Ave., Dnipro, 49005, Ukraine

³Department of Mechanical Engineering, Dniprovsk State Technical University,
2 Dniprobudivska Ave., Kamianske, 51918, Ukraine

^abelmas09@meta.ua, ^bkolosov.d.l@nmu.one, ^conyshchenko.s.v@nmu.one,
^dbilouselena66@gmail.com, ^ehannaivan71@gmail.com, ^fantonovakv@gmail.com

Keywords: Stay Rope, Cable-Stayed Structure, Orthotropic Composite, Reinforcing Element, Breakage, Stress-Strain State, Local Disturbance, Fiber Displacement, Internal Loading Forces, Tangential Stress.

Abstract. The purpose of research is to justify a calculation method for a stay rope of composite fiber structure with a breakage in fiber continuity. Research methodology is in constructing and solving a deformation model of a composite fiber stay rope with continuity breakage of one of its fibers. The calculation method of a stress-strain state of a stay rope of composite fiber structure considering the breakage of one of its fibers is established. The scientific novelty of research is in determining that the length of manifestation of a local disturbance of a stress-strain state of composite stay rope is proportional to a square root of a ratio of tensile modulus of a reinforcing element material and shear modulus of an elastic material that connects them. The practical value of the research is in that the calculation method allows reasonable prediction of a tractive capacity loss of a stay rope as a result of breakage of any of its reinforcing elements. The known value of residual tractive capacity allows reasonable selection of a safety margin for a stay rope, which ensures a sufficient level of reliability of a cable-stayed bridge.

Introduction

Steel-reinforced concrete cable-stayed structures, including cable-stayed bridges, are less material-intensive, more technological in manufacturing and construction. Increased reliability conditions are applied to them, as for buildings used by people. A significant amount of study has been done to research a stress-strain state (SSS) of cable-stayed structures. The design of wide-span cable-stayed structures is justified in [1]. In article [2], a calculation of a ceiling for a unit load in the joints of the bottom boom is performed. Monograph [3] describes spatial cable-stayed steel-reinforced concrete structures. Methods of calculation and construction are suggested. A stress-strain state of steel-reinforced concrete cable-stayed coverings is studied theoretically and experimentally in [4].

Stay ropes are affected by the environment. Its negative impact must be minimized, in particular by putting a system of parallel cables into an elastic shell. This solution is used in rubber-cable ropes. An elastic shell protects cables from interaction with the environment. The latter makes it possible to manufacture stay ropes using reinforcing cables of smaller diameters. They use wires of a smaller diameter. The ultimate strength is higher for wires with a smaller diameter. Bending rigidity is lower for cables with a smaller diameter. This allows placing cables in layers in composite stay ropes. In [5], a design of two-layer rubber-cable belts of conveyors is justified.

The cross-sectional shape of a stay rope affects its resistance to wind loads. It is possible to reduce the resistance by increasing the width of a thinner stay rope. Elements of structures sometimes break during operation, including cables in ropes. Breakage of a cable, as an element of rope reinforcement,